

Impact of the Documentary "Virunga" on Youth Attitudes Toward Biodiversity Conservation

Introduction

As part of a seminar focused on biodiversity conservation, participants watched the documentary *Virunga*, which highlights the complex issues surrounding the protection of Virunga National Park in the Democratic Republic of Congo. The park is a UNESCO World Heritage Site, home to critically endangered species like the mountain gorilla, and is under threat from illegal resource exploitation, poaching, and armed conflict. *Virunga* follows the efforts of park rangers and conservationists to protect the area, drawing attention to the intersection of conservation, corporate interests, and local communities.

Before and after the film, participants completed surveys designed to assess their knowledge and attitudes toward biodiversity conservation, their familiarity with the situation in the Democratic Republic of Congo and Virunga National Park, as well as their willingness to engage in local conservation efforts. Below is an analysis of the results from both surveys, followed by a comparison of key findings.

The questions that coincide in both surveys are the following: How familiar are you with the situation in Virunga National Park?; How important do you think the conservation of biodiversity in protected areas like Virunga is for the global ecosystem?; Which factors do you consider the biggest threats to biodiversity in protected areas like Virunga?; In your opinion, what impact do corporations have on biodiversity conservation in protected areas like Virunga?; How effective do you believe watching documentaries like "Virunga" is in raising awareness about biodiversity conservation compared to other methods (social media, classroom education, news outlets, etc.)?; How do you feel your actions or lifestyle impact biodiversity and conservation efforts?; How likely are you to engage in local conservation activities or initiatives?

Also, in the second research, the following questions were added: How relevant are the issues highlighted in "Virunga" to your personal experience and interests in urban biodiversity conservation?; In what ways do you think "Virunga" effectively engages young people in conservation efforts?; What type of follow-up activities would make you more interested in

engaging in biodiversity conservation after watching "Virunga"?; What challenges do you think might limit the effectiveness of using films like "Virunga" to engage urban youth in conservation?

Looking at the results of the first survey, it can be concluded that the participants had no knowledge about the situation in "Virunga" National Park, with 100% stating they were not familiar with it. In contrast, the second survey indicated a significant shift in awareness, as 50% of participants reported being familiar with the park after watching the film. Regarding the importance of "Virunga" for the global ecosystem, 71.4% of respondents in the first survey were neutral, whereas post-film, 100% of participants acknowledged its importance.

In the first survey, 57% of participants identified climate change and habitat loss as the biggest threats to the park's survival. This perspective remained consistent in the second survey, where all respondents recognized these threats, underscoring a unified understanding of the challenges faced by biodiversity.

Moreover, while more than half (57%) of participants in the first survey were neutral about the influence of global corporations on biodiversity conservation, the second survey showed a significant change, with 83.3% viewing corporate actions as extremely negative. In terms of the effectiveness of documentaries like "Virunga" compared to other methods of spreading awareness, the first survey revealed that a majority were neutral. However, post-film, participants mostly believed that documentaries were very effective in raising awareness.

When discussing the impact of their actions on biodiversity, 71% of respondents in the first survey considered their influence to be moderate. In contrast, in the second survey, only 33.3% maintained a moderate view, with 50% now believing their actions were very impactful. Additionally, while 71% expressed interest in concrete social engagement in the first survey, this number rose to 83.3% post-film, indicating a greater willingness to participate in local conservation activities.